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Water Health Open knowLedge (WHOW)

Final version of the network of ontologies is ready

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<p style="text-align: center;">Abstract</p>	<p>The main goal of the WHOW project is to build an open and distributed knowledge graph that is capable of integrating and standardising heterogeneous data of the environmental and health domains coming from several data sources and available in different formats and structures.</p> <p>The ultimate goal is fostering the creation of innovative applications, services and studies on top of the WHOW knowledge graph.</p> <p>The document presents the final version of the ontology network defined in the context of the WHOW project. An ontology network is a collection of ontologies related together via a variety of relationships, such as alignment, modularization, version, and dependency. Hence, a networked ontology is an ontology included in such a network, sharing relationships with a potentially large number of other ontologies. This characteristic enables modularisation and maximises interoperability with other semantic assets. The ontology network developed counts of five ontologies, that is: (i) Hydrography ontology, (ii) Water monitoring ontology, (iii) Water indicator ontology, (iv) Weather Monitoring ontology, (v) Health Monitoring ontology.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Keywords</p>	<p>Ontology Design, Ontology Design Patterns, Ontology Networks, Knowledge Engineering, Water, Health</p>

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Version	Date	Organisation	Description
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0.4	2023-12-28	CNR-ISTC	Integration of reviewers' comments
0.5	2023-12-29	CNR-ISTC	Final revision and global editing

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Executive Summary

The main goal of the WHOW project is to build an open and distributed knowledge graph that is capable of integrating and standardising heterogeneous data of the environmental and health domains coming from several data sources and available in different formats and structures.

The ultimate goal is fostering the creation of innovative applications, services and studies on top of the WHOW knowledge graph.

Besides the business use cases that are going to be extensively described in deliverable D2.1 to be released at the end of December 2021, a key aspect of the WHOW project is the design of a fully distributed technical architecture for effective creation and publication of the WHOW open and distributed knowledge graph.

Thus, this document presents the final version of the ontology network defined in the context of the WHOW project. According to [1], an ontology network is a collection of ontologies related together via a variety of relationships, such as alignment, modularization, version, and dependency. Hence, a networked ontology is an ontology included in such a network, sharing relationships with a potentially large number of other ontologies. This characteristic enables modularisation and maximises interoperability with other semantic assets.

1. Introduction

This is the Deliverable 3.3 that presents the results related to the milestone #6 “Final version of the network of ontologies is ready”. The document results from the activities conducted in the context of the task 3.1 of Activity 3 related to “Knowledge graph definition”.

1.1 Project Overview

The WHOW project aims to foster the creation of the first open and distributed European knowledge graph on water consumption and quality, health parameters and dissemination of diseases to be reused for advanced analysis and development of innovative services.

The project leverages the Linked Open Data paradigm. Water related datasets from Italy and other European countries and Copernicus (the European Union's Earth observation programme) will be used to support the construction of WHOW's knowledge graph, intended as a federation of knowledge graphs deployed at each data provider willing to join the WHOW community. The knowledge graph will be documented on data.europa.eu, the official portal for European data, thanks to the adoption of shared metadata models such as DCAT-AP and its extensions that are relevant for the type of data treated in WHOW (e.g., GeoDCAT-AP). Selected health related datasets mainly from Italy will be linked to specific water datasets.

WHOW targets identified use cases in the creation of the knowledge graph. In order to evaluate such use cases relevant sets of indicators for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are identified along with Key Performance Indicators for metadata and data quality. A co-creation programme, where interested stakeholders and users are engaged from the initial phases of the project, is set-up so as to consider real needs of data re-users.

The initiative supports the Public Open Data Digital Service Infrastructure by helping to boost the development of information products and services based on the re-use and combination of environmental data and health data on disease dissemination.

1.2 Objectives

The objective of the activity 3.1 is the construction of a networked ontology for representing knowledge related to water quality parameters and sanitation. The ontology network has to be designed by following an agile methodology for knowledge engineering called *eXtreme Design* [2] (XD). XD emphasises the reuse of ontology design patterns [3] (ODPs) into an iterative and incremental process. More interestingly, XD is a collaborative methodology that fosters the cooperation among multiple actors with different roles (e.g. knowledge engineers, domain experts, etc.) to make sure all the modelling requirements are first captured and then effectively covered. Hence, we opted for XD since it fits our collaborative setting based on the co-creation programme. Furthermore, there is evidence in literature [4] that the reuse of ODPs (i) speeds up the ontology design process, (ii) eases design choices, (iii) produces more effective results in terms of ontology quality, and (iv) boosts interoperability.

1.3 Relationships with other activities

The present Deliverable D3.3 is another important milestone (#6) of the WHOW project. It covers all the activities of task 3.1 of Activity 3 that have dependencies linked with other tasks of other activities of the project.

The following Figure 1 shows such relationships. In particular, the content of this deliverable; that is, (i) the results of the activities of task 3.1, is related to the definition of the use cases (i.e. Deliverable 2.1 [5]), (ii) the deployment of the technical architecture (i.e. Deliverable 4.2 [6]), and (iii) the compliance with the Metadata Quality Assurance (MQA) tool for datasets (i.e. Deliverable 5.3 [7]).

Figure 1. Relationships with other deliverables and activities.

1.4 Structure of the document

The rest of this document is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) describes the WHOW Ontology Network. [Section 3](#) provides usage examples of the ontology network and details about its deployment. Finally, [Section 4](#) concludes the document.

2. The WHOW Network of Ontologies

The WHOW ontology network consists of 5 ontology modules and 3 ontology modules of the partner ISPRA that have been revised during the WHOW project and extensively re-used, with a direct approach[8], as the basis for the definition of the WHOW ontologies. The overall network and interactions with other ontologies is shown In Figure 1 where each ontology is represented as a circle, whilst the arrows represent owl:imports axioms among the ontologies. The WHOW network is represented by the gray circles. Its base namespace is <https://w3id.org/italia/whow/onto/> and from this base namespace each module defines its local namespace following the table of prefixes reported in Figure 1. We decided to follow the 10 rules for persistent URIs for the ontologies and linked open data and we have chosen to use the w3id.org service for neutral and persistent URIs. Although whow is the name of our project and it is not recommended using project names for URIs, we in any case use it since it is an acronym of the two main important domains we investigated during the last three years. This guarantees sustainability over time of the URIs that can persist independently of the end of the WHOW project.

The network is: (i) under version control on GitHub¹; (ii) shared on Zenodo² with a CC-BY 4.0 International licence; and (iii) findable on Linked Open Vocabularies³.

We are currently in an open dialogue with the Italian Department of Digital Transformation in order to let them harvest the ontologies in the Italian national catalogue of semantic assets schema.gov.it.

Figure 2. WHOW network of ontology and its interaction with ISPRA's ontologies.

¹ <https://github.com/whow-project/assets/tree/main/ontologies>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/7916179>

³ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

In the following sections, we describe each WHOW ontology that has been developed during the project. Overall, the ontologies, together with the produced linked open data at each data provider, form the knowledge graph layer of the WHOW technical architecture.

1.1 Hydrography ontology

The *Hydrography ontology*⁴ (prefix `hydro`) represents a general-purpose hydrological taxonomy following the definitions given in the European Directive 2000/60/EC⁵. The ontology is depicted in Figure 2 using Graffoo⁶ as graphical reference notation.

Figure 3. The Hydrography Ontology.

The blue rectangle is a class of the ISPRA ontology directly re-used in the WHOW network and the yellow rectangles are the classes of the hydrography ontology we defined.

The top-level class is `hydro:WaterFeature`, a subclass of the ISPRA ontology `ispra-emf:FeatureOfInterest` with `hydro:WaterBasin` and `hydro:WaterBody` as subclasses. A `hydro:WaterBody` further specialises into a number of subclasses defining a clear

⁴ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/hydrography>

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32000L0060&rid=2>

⁶ <https://essepuntato.it/graffoo/>

classification among the different types of water bodies (e.g., lake water body, river water body, etc.). In this ontology we reused the part of ODP⁷ for expressing parthood between water basins (cf. the object property `hydro:isSubWaterBasin`).

1.2 Water monitoring ontology

The *Water Monitoring Ontology*⁸ is one of the most important ontologies of the WHOW network. It is identified by the prefix `w-mon`. It provides means to represent observations related to the quality of water courses, such as chemical and biological substances found in water bodies, and to physical elements (e.g., the height of lakes). It also includes means to model the quality observed for the water for human consumption, and its level of radioactivity. The requirements for the representation of water observations are defined according to the data provided by the data providers involved in the project and the standards and directives in terms of observations and water-related assessments.

As far as the representation of water observations is concern, it is possible to refer to European directives: (i) those deriving from taxonomies from European Directive 98/83/CE (and subsequent ones), confirmed by the Italian Ministry of Health concerning parameters of the waters for human consumption, and (ii) those deriving from the European Directive 2009/90/EC³⁷, concerning parameters of surface waters.

Thus, water quality monitoring requires the integration of heterogeneous types of both observations and observation objects derived from samplers. As a result, in the ontology (as shown in Figure 3), a `w-mon:WaterObservation` is divided into `w-mon:DrinkingWaterObservation`, and `w-mon:`

`SurfaceOrGroundWaterObservation` which are, in turn, further divided into subclasses based on the specific parameter being observed. In fact, the observations that have as an object a microbiological agent or a chemical substance, monitor it through its concentration in the water.

On the contrary, observations on properties of water, such as hardness, density or pH, do not imply the presence of an object being observed since no chemical substance or microbiological agent is implied there. In addition, we also model observation regarding radioactivity. This is captured by the use of the class named `w-mon:RadioactivityObservation`.

The ontology follows the Stimulus-Sensor-Observation Ontology Design Pattern (SSO ODP), which is a standard for the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe, and the Specimen model of ISO 19156:201138, which outlines the properties of sampling process features.

This ontology is used to support the use cases 1, 2 and 3 of the WHOW project.

1.3 Water Indicator ontology

The Water Indicator ontology⁹, with prefix `w-ind`, re-uses the *Indicator* ontology design pattern defined in OntoPiA¹⁰, which is the Italian national network of ontologies and controlled vocabularies currently documented in the Italian national catalogue of semantic assets, schema.gov.it. This pattern is re-used to address indicators and metrics for the indicator calculation of water quality.

⁷ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:PartOf>

⁸ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/water-monitoring>

⁹ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/water-indicator>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/italia/daf-ontologie-vocabolari-controllati>

As shown in Figure 4, there is a class representing the calculation of an indicator `w-ind:WaterIndicatorCalculation` which is specific for waters (an example can be the LTLeco indicators for lakes) and extends the general pattern included in the national ontology `Indicator` aforementioned. That class represents an n-ary relation that put together the `w-ind:WaterIndicator`, its value, the `hydro:WaterFeature` being monitored and defined in the Hydrography ontology and the time in which the indicator has been calculated. Note that, being the `w-ind:WaterIndicator` a subclass of the national defined `indicator:Indicator` class, which allows one to define a hierarchy among indicators, also water indicators can be defined as a composition of other indicators (as in the case of the LTLeco of lakes).

Figure 5. Water Indicator Ontology.

This ontology is used to support the use cases 2 of the WHOW project.

1.4 Weather Monitoring ontology

The Weather Monitoring Ontology¹¹, identified by the prefix `wh-mon`. Similarly to the Water Monitoring ontology, this ontology, shown in Figure 5, has its focus on a `wh-mon:WeatherObservation` related to a `wh-mon:WeatherFeatureOfInterest` (either ground-level soil, air, wind, snow or rainfall), a `wh-mon:WeatherObservableProperty` (e.g., the observable temperature of the air)

¹¹ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/weather-monitoring>

and observed by a `wh-mon:WeatherSensor` usually hosted by a `wh-mon:WeatherStation`. It reuses the ISPRa ontology network to model observations, which in turn is fully semantically aligned with the national IoT ontology of the OntoPiA network, and related properties; its main pattern is the one used in the water monitoring ontology and in the Semantic Sensor Network , a Web Recommendation of W3C¹².

Figure 6. The Weather Monitoring Ontology.

This model is meant to address the need to represent weather observations that could serve as a basis to derive information on extreme events monitoring and prediction, such as rainfalls and snow levels. In essence, this ontology has been defined in order to support the use case 3 of the WHOW project.

1.5 Health Monitoring ontology

Finally, the Health Monitoring ontology¹³, whose prefix is `hm` reuses the OntoPiA Indicator ontology and focuses on the representation of health indicators coming from regional healthcare facilities in order to monitoring specific health parameters. Examples include drug distribution rates and hospital accesses according to disease code and facility involved.

Figure 6 illustrates the graphical representation of the ontology.

¹² <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

¹³ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/health-monitoring>

Figure 7. The Health Monitoring Ontology.

Different types of `hm:HealthcareIndicatorCalculation` are defined, based on the typology of indicator they describe, i.e. infectious disease rate, death rates related to diagnosis, average hospital stay and drug distribution. The indicator calculation also refers to a statistical dimension class, i.e., the `hm:ClinicalCohort`, which specifies the population referred to as defined by a number of criteria, that is `hm:CohortCriteriaDescription`, such as age and gender and concepts (e.g., drug being monitored, disease, caused of deaths).

Notably, the ontology also introduces the concept of `hm:HealthOrganisation` that can be defined as the single hospital or the `hm:HealthcareAuthority`. This latter represents a division of the region (in Italy the health sector is under the responsibility of the various regions) territory under which the healthcare authority exercises its control and mission.

This ontology has been defined in order to support specifically the use case 2 of the WHOW project.

3. Ontology Network Usage

Figure 8 shows the architectural deployment of the ontology network applied both in case of ARIA and ISPRA. In this deployment the Triplestore component of the WHOW Toolkit retrieves an ontology from the GitHub repository for ontologies when it is requested by an end-user. Then the ontology is served to an end-user always as HTML through LODE.

Figure 8. The architectural deployment of the ontology network.

Healthcare Indicator Monitoring Ontology

IRI: <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/health-monitoring>

Version IRI: <urn:absolute:https://w3id.org/whow/onto/health-monitoring/0.3>

Current version : Version 0.3 - June 2023 - modified some elements of the ontology (introduction of the property hasScope for the Cohort and related elements, revision of the organisations involved in the computation of some indicators)

Imported Ontologies : <https://w3id.org/italia/env/onto/top> ([visualise it with LODE](#))

Other visualisation : [Ontology source](#) - [WebVowl](#)

Table of Content

1. [Classes](#)
2. [Object Properties](#)
3. [Data Properties](#)
4. [Annotation Properties](#)
5. [Namespace Declarations](#)

Prefixes	
.	https://w3id.org/whow/onto/health-monitoring/
ispra-top:	https://w3id.org/italia/env/onto/top/
ispra-emf:	https://w3id.org/italia/env/onto/inspire-mf/
ispra-plc:	https://w3id.org/italia/env/onto/place/
rdfs:	http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#

Figure 9. shows the HTML visualisation of the Health Monitoring Ontology presented by LODE.

Instead, Figure 9 shows the HTML visualisation displayed by LOD2 when a user accesses an ontology through her browser.

Finally, if a user or an application requires a machine readable serialisation of an ontology, then it is possible to get it through content negotiation. For example the following is a cURL request that allows one to get the same ontology as before serialised as Turtle.

```
curl -kL -H "Accept: text/turtle" \  
https://w3id.org/whow/onto/health-monitoring
```

4. Conclusions

Thus, this document presents the final version of the ontology network defined in the context of the WHOW project. According to [1], an ontology network is a collection of ontologies related together via a variety of relationships, such as alignment, modularization, version, and dependency. Hence, a networked ontology is an ontology included in such a network, sharing relationships with a potentially large number of other ontologies. This characteristic enables modularisation and maximises interoperability with other semantic assets. The ontology network developed counts of five ontologies, that is: (i) Hydrography ontology, (ii) Water monitoring ontology, (iii) Water indicator ontology, (iv) Weather Monitoring ontology, (v) Health Monitoring ontology.

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